

**THE LEGAL GROUNDS OF AN APPLICATION OF SOME ELEMENTS
OF THE COMMON LAW (ENGLISH LAW) IN THE CURRENT LEGAL
SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

Umida Bekmirzayeva

4th year student of the Faculty of International Law of the

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

ubekmirzayeva@inbox.ru

+99899 824-72-90

*Academic Supervisor: **Yusuvaliyeva Rahima Yusupovna***

Professor of "Theory of Law and Public Administration"

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Abstract: *This article deals with the need to introduce some elements of common (English) law into the legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan to increase the investment attractiveness of the country. It is quite notable that Uzbekistan is experiencing great reforms in all fields of society in the same way legal system is not an exception. The choice of English law is one of the most popular in international investment and corporate transactions. There are a number of reasons for this, one of the main ones being that English law has a well-known, well-developed and reputable jurisprudence. However, The republic of Uzbekistan has already shaped its own national legal system based on the main principles of civil law family. In this article, it is said not to copy all of institutions of common (English law) system but also to conduct research on the applications of most efficient elements of this legal family and addressed to the experience of a neighbouring country, Kazakhstan. In addition, various ways in which elements of English law might be implemented in Uzbekistan are discussed.*

Keywords: legal system, common law, civil law, mixed legal system, English law, element, the principle of estoppel, free economic zone, international financial center, investors.

The process of globalization has already penetrated into every sphere of our lives. This means that nothing is stable now, and this rule also applies to legal systems. In comparative law, the term "legal system" is used in three senses: first, in the socio-economic sense (in this case, it generally corresponds to the concept of "socio-economic type of law"); second, in the sense of a country's legal system; and third, in the sense of the unity of the legal systems of different countries.¹

Below is a legal map of the modern world to give you an idea of how widespread these legal systems are:

¹ Hayitboev F.P., Najimov M.K. Basic modern legal systems (Comparative Law) / Editor-in-Chief A.Kh. Saidov. Textbook - T.: TSU, 2016. - 250 p.

The Republic of Uzbekistan, as a state belonging to civil legal family, is characterized by the fact that normative legal acts are the main source of law and its systematization. Considering that the formation of the current national legal system began in 1991, as a state with a database of more than 35,000 normative legal acts² in all spheres of social life, it has always been important to systematize legislation. However, English (common law) has a number of advantages, and the practice of using English law has been established in the PRC, the UAE, Singapore, and other countries. The time-tested experience of the developed countries of the world shows that the partial introduction of some legal elements of common law in other legal systems (families)³ leads to positive results. These countries are Japan, Israel, Ethiopia, PRC, JAR, Philippines, Cyprus. and in theory they are mainly called “Mixed Legal Systems⁴”. However, through time, the definition of a mixed legal system changed and later, mixed legal systems were defined as having the following characteristics: (i) civil law rules and principles are filtered through Anglo-American institutions, for instance, the common law judge; (ii) judicial decisions are given strong precedential value whether the civil law is codified or not; (iii) civil procedure is adversarial and Anglo-American, with an emphasis on remedies that leaves an imprint on substantive civil law; (iv) common law makes incursions into the civil law sphere by penetrating the most porous point of entry, such as the law of delict, while leaving resistant institutions such as property law relatively unaffected; and (v) commercial law is transformed and replaced by Anglo-American commercial law, because of pressure to conform to the norms of the dominant economy⁵.

² <https://lex.uz/uz/>

³ Маркова-Мурашова С. А. Смешанные правовые системы // Вестник СанктПетербургского университета МВД России. — 2006. — № 1 (29). — С. 24—31.

⁴ Даниелян А. С. Феномен смешанных правовых систем как пример сближения правовых культур // Известия ТулГУ. Экономические и юридические науки. — 2016. — № 1—2. — С. 157—163; Du Plessis J. *Comparative Law and the Study of Mixed Legal Systems*. — Oxford University Press, 2006.

⁵ SMITH, ‘The Preservation of the Civilian Tradition in “Mixed Jurisdictions”’ in YANNOPOULOS (ed.), *Civil Law in the Modern World*, Louisiana State University Press, Baton Rouge: 1965, p. 4.

In particular, in the neighboring Republic of Kazakhstan, both territorially and legally, attempts to incorporate certain elements of English law, especially in the field of business law, began with the 1998 reforms.⁶ However, these attempts did not work efficiently due to the fact that some elements of national and English law were not well studied sufficiently. Only with the establishment of the Astana-International Financial Center on July 5, 2018, these endeavors commenced to justify themselves. As a result of economic and legal reforms, Kazakhstan's GDP grew by 9.2%. Now without any hesitation it can be stated that Kazakhstan is currently experiencing a turning point in its legal history and some elements deriving of a common law system are to be implemented into the national legal system which has its roots in the civilian legal tradition. This move might mean that Kazakhstan is on the verge of becoming one of the ‘mixed legal systems’ which are a hybrid form of legal system at the intersection of common law and civil law⁷.

Kazakh lawyers consider the following institutions of the English doctrine of common law to be important for the countries of civil law:

- First of all, the issue of separating legal entities and their legal capacity⁸, in particular, the issue of their liability from the liability of its founders, is very important today.
- Liquidation (experience) of enterprises with a state share;
- Incorporate the definition of corporate governance into the Civil Code;
- Introduce the principle of "next control";
- Abolition of compulsory membership in self-governing associations.

The aforementioned norms are equally important for the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the issue of separation of the responsibility of the heads and founders of the enterprise from the responsibility of legal entities is considered to be

⁶ Сулейменов Майдан Кунтуарович. "Английское право и правовая система Казахстана" Вестник Института законодательства и правовой информации Республики Казахстан, no. 5 (41), 2015, pp. 169-181.

⁷ Krausenboeck Maria (2017). Common law, civilian legal systems and mixed legal systems: implications for the implementation of elements of English law in Kazakhstan. Вестник Института законодательства и правовой информации Республики Казахстан, (2 (47)), 59-65.

⁸ Salomon v A Salomon & Co Ltd [1896] UKHL 1, [1897]

important This debate has been going on since the adoption of the Criminal Code and the Code of Administrative Response of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Only the new Code of Administrative Response, which is currently being adopted, is the issue of liability of legal entities.

It would not be a mistake to say that the removal of the requirement for the minimum amount of authorized capital (authorized fund) in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, namely, now this requirement is set only in certain license requirements, in some cases this change undermines the rights of creditors. In this case, the British and The introduction of the "next control" principle, which has already been tested in the American economy, can lead to positive results in our country.

Furthermore, In English law, legal entities are not forced to become members of any public association on a compulsory basis. Article 77 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that individuals, in particular commercial organizations, coordinate their business activities, as well as non-profit organizations may join associations (allies) and other associations in order to represent and protect their common property interests. Nevertheless, this merger should be a choice based on the principles of complete freedom and voluntariness. Unfortunately, in practice including membership in farmers' associations is compulsory for every farmer.

In addition to this, in English law, the norms related to the representations (representative offices) formed over the years by the court precedent and therefore analysis of the positive aspects of this issue should not be neglected.

Moreover, Estoppel is said to be a principle unique to the English legal system. To understand the value of the principle within the sphere of English law, one must understand how the English law of contracts is based on the idea of consideration (in other words: the idea of ‘quid pro quo’). This means that unilateral promises are not enforceable. This is in stark contrast to the contract law in civilian legal systems, which is based on the idea of cause, and therefore effect can be given to unilateral

promises.⁹ However, not enforcing unilateral promises can, at times, lead to an unfair result.¹⁰ Although the set of norms on damages is classified in detail in the civil law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there is a perception of the lost benefit as indirect damage, and in practice proving it is a problem for the parties to the process. The existing norms in English law would make it easier for the parties.

In summary, the Republic of Uzbekistan has already launched measures to study English law and implement some elements. The Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev was responsible to study the prospects of the practice of application. In particular, it was reported that proposals have been prepared for the introduction of certain norms of English law in the territory of the Navoi Free Economic Zone in the very near future.

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¹⁰ Central London Property Trust Ltd. v High Trees House Ltd. [1947] KB 130, [Jones \(AE\) v Jones \(FW\) \[1977\] 1 WLR 438](#)

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